

**Impacts of investments for regional and local development: The Case of
Istanbul, Turkey**

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Abstract

The tourism sector enables countries to reduce unemployment levels and attract foreign direct investment (FDI) which increase public welfare and economic activity. In this respect, it has a critical importance for specifically developing countries. In this article, the importance of tourism for developing countries will be mentioned and numerical data related to the sector will be presented. Among the developing countries, the example of Turkey, where tourism is of great importance, was chosen. The number of tourists, the share of tourism income in GDP, the share of the tourism sector in FDI and the employment opportunities provided by the tourism sector have been examined through the example of, Istanbul, which has developed in the tourism sector since the 1980s. Based on the mentioned criteria, the importance of the tourism sector for Turkish economy has been tried to be revealed.

Keywords: Tourism Sector, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Public Welfare, Economy, GDP

Introduction

Tourism plays a crucial role in providing large volume of foreign exchange flows which contribute positively to the economic and social development of the country as a whole. Thus developing countries such as Turkey desperately need foreign resources in order to ensure its development. Until the 1980s, the insufficient accommodation, transportation capacities and other factors such as terror were the main causes of Turkey having the low market share in the tourism industry. As economic distress increased the government gave more importance to tourism sector in its investment plans. Turkey initiated its tourism investment moves in 1982 and it ranked 20th and 4th in 2000 and 2021 accordingly in terms of number of tourists in the world.

Istanbul is one of the most visited cities in Turkey, it attracted more than 9M

tourists in 2021 which is equivalent to 30% of number of total tourists in Turkey as you can see in Figure 1.

Istanbul is well known about its historical, socio-cultural and economic aspects. It is one of the oldest cities in the world and it was the capital of many empires such as Roman Empire, Byzantine Empire, Latin Empire, Ottoman Empire. Its 8500 year-old history show itself in palaces, museums, excavation sites and streets where daily life continues. It has a strategic location as the Western part of the city is in Europe and the Eastern is in Asia, the Bosphorus bridge connects the two continents. This geographical location is extremely important for socio-cultural integration as the city has characteristics of East and West at the same time.

Improvement and diversification of transportation, accommodation and infrastructure and development of quality divided roads, cruise and marinas, airports have made tourist visits more comfortable and accessible. Tourism investments in Istanbul have stimulated the economy at the local and national levels and hence increasing the economic welfare of Turkey over the long-term by stimulating production level and attracting FDI. For example, tourism receives input from 54 different sectors for service delivery so when the final demand increases by 1 unit there is an increase of 1.99 unit in production activities throughout the economy. On the other hand, since the return period on investments is relatively shorter and capital investments required to employ one person are lower, tourism sector generates employment opportunities for residents. Despite

some negative aspects of tourism, it plays an important role in the development of a country by stimulating the economy and decreasing unemployment.

During the research, the primary task was to find an answer to the question of how investments in tourism sector contribute to the development of a country. In this research paper, Istanbul is taken as an example. Secondary data analysis and archival study methods were used to conduct the research.

Research on Importance of Tourism Investments for Istanbul

Economic Factors

As depicted in Figure 2, tourism revenues increased by 103% compared to the previous year and reached 24 billion 482 million 332 thousand dollars and the share of tourism income in GDP happened to be 3% in 2021. Istanbul contributed 30% of the total tourism income with almost 1% share in total GDP in 2021. Tourism sector is in the top 10 among the sectors that make up GDP for almost every year. So tourism is an extremely important income source for the local and national residents.

Year	Total Tourism Income (1000 \$)	The Share of Tourism Income in GDP (%)
2010	24.930.997	3,2
2011	28.115.692	3,4
2012	29.007.003	3,3
2013	32.308.991	3,4
2014	34.305.903	3,7
2015	31.464.777	3,7
2016	22.107.440	2,6
2017	26.283.656	3,1
2018	29.512.926	3,8
2019	34.520.332	4,6
2020*	12.059.320	1,6
2021	24.482.300	3

Source: <https://www.tursab.org.tr>

*Since income level could not be measured due to the Covid-19 pandemic, income data of second quarter could not be included to the total income in 2020.

Figure 2

The number of foreign tourists visiting Turkey and Istanbul increased by 94% and 80% accordingly when compared to the same period of the previous year (See Figure 2). Results show that there exists a significant relationship between the number of tourists and FDI which is an important factor for the development of an economy (Fauzel, Sheereen&Seetana, Boopen&Sannasee, Raja, 2016). Figure 3 illustrates the foreign direct investments in Turkey between 1970-2020. The ratio of direct investments has increased especially after liberal policies implemented in 1980.

Figure 3-Foreign Direct Investments in Turkey (1970-2020). Source: The World Bank.

Sectors	Years										
	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Agriculture	524	523	769	807	1.067	777	730	1.354	377	798	1.396
Industry	66.112	55.268	80.99	63.054	78.582	66.427	56.228	80.296	39.123	46.515	92.237
Tertiary	114.535	75.121	102.008	79.614	95.153	80.383	79.477	101.071	92.703	101.621	124.11
Total	181.171	130.912	183.767	143.475	174.802	147.587	136.435	182.721	132.203	148.934	217.743

Figure 4-Direct Investments of Non-Residents in Turkey – Sectoral Breakdown (Million USD). Source: CBRT(Central Bank of Republic of Turkey); <http://tcmb.gov.tr,ET.25.05.2022>)

Figure 4 shows the Foreign Direct Investments with sectoral breakdown between 2010 and 2020. Sectoral distribution of Direct Investments in Turkey shows that services (tertiary) sector, including the tourism industry, takes the highest share.

Therefore, it can be said that tourism has a positive impact on the economic development of a country.

Employment Factors

Foreign direct investments have a significant effect on employment opportunities. As tourism sector plays an important role in attracting FDI, it directly affects employment levels. Total number of employed people in Turkey is 13.7 M (See Figure 5). Around 1M people worked in accommodation and food sector which is equivalent to 13,5% within trade and food sector (See Figure 6). In 2021, while the total accommodation capacity in Turkey recorded around 1.8 M, Istanbul shares 13% of it which means more than 13% of employed people in Istanbul work for tourism industry. Therefore, it is clear that tourism sector in Istanbul and Turkey generates new employment opportunities and decreases unemployment levels. This fact positively contributes to public welfare of Turkey.

Figure 5: Total Number of Paid Workers in Turkey, June 2021. Source: <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=37503&dil=2>

Distribution of paid employees by sector, June 2021

Sector	Number of Paid Employee			Annual change (%)
	June 2021	June 2020	Annual difference	
B-N - Industry, construction, trade and services	13 701 941	12 072 275	1 629 666	13.5
B-E - Industry	4 723 371	4 183 122	540 249	12.9
B - Mining and quarrying	137 307	124 377	12 930	10.4
C - Manufacturing	4 399 762	3 882 605	517 157	13.3
D - Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	118 663	114 188	4 475	3.9
E - Water supply, sewerage, waste management and remediation activities	67 639	61 952	5 687	9.2
F - Construction	1 515 999	1 227 425	288 574	23.5
G-N - Trade and services	7 462 571	6 661 728	800 843	12.0
G - Trade	3 049 186	2 774 414	274 772	9.9
H - Transportation and storage	1 023 850	909 278	114 572	12.6
I - Accommodation and food service activities	1 009 636	871 712	137 924	15.8
J - Information and communication	243 362	206 405	36 957	17.9
K - Financial and insurance activities	202 054	203 658	-1 604	-0.8
L - Real estate activities	98 330	83 080	15 250	18.4
M - Professional, scientific and technical activities	616 515	517 632	98 883	19.1
N - Administrative and support service	1 219 638	1 095 549	124 089	11.3

Figure 6: Distribution of paid employees by sector, June 2021. Source: <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=37503&dil>

Conclusion

Tourism investments in Istanbul are source of high employment levels and economic growth at local and national levels as Istanbul plays an important role in tourism industry in Turkey. It stimulates the economy by increasing GDP, reducing unemployment and attracting FDI which escalate the public welfare. Due to the development of infrastructures, accommodation capacities and transportation facilities in Istanbul it attracts more international tourists every year which encourages foreign exchange inflows to the country. Increase in GDP, FDI and employment ultimately help a developing country to reach the resources it needs to ensure its development in the long run.

The secondary data and archival analysis show that there is a positive correlation between the economic growth of a developing country and tourism investments. The data affirms that as tourism investments raise it increases number of tourists which has a positive effect on Foreign Direct Investments. Ultimately, this cycle increases public welfare and economic activity of a developing country.

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